

Local Government in Austria

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Alexandra Schantl, Dalilah Pichler and Thomas Prorok

KDZ - Centre for Public Administration Research Austria

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism

University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse
Ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

Faculty of Political Science
and International Studies
University of Warsaw
University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

UNIVERSIDAD
NACIONAL DE
SAN MARTÍN

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

जवाहरलाल नेहरू विश्वविद्यालय
Jawaharlal Nehru University

Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

Western
UNIVERSITY · CANADA
University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Austria is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

KDZ – Centre for Public Administration Research
Austria: Alexandra Schantl, Dalilah Pichler, Thomas Prorok
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Marvin Van Hagen/Unsplash

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Austria	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Austria: An Introduction	6
2.2. <i>Organization of Public Transport in Austria Focusing on Functional Urban Regions (City Regions)</i>	11
2.3. <i>Municipal Water and Wastewater Management in Austria</i>	16
2.4. <i>Social Housing: The Case of Vienna</i>	21
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Austria: An Introduction	29
3.2. <i>Budget Transparency with Open Spending Austria</i>	33
3.3. <i>Effects of the Intragovernmental Transfer System on Financial Strength</i>	38
3.4. <i>The Role of EU Structural Funds for Austrian Local Governments and its Contribution to the Urban-Rural Interplay</i>	43
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Austria: An Introduction	49
4.2. <i>Inter-Municipal Development Process ‘Lienzer Talboden’ Future Space</i>	55
4.3. <i>Administrative Association in Building Law: Region Vorderland</i>	60
4.4. <i>Post-Merger Evaluation: Future-Oriented Organizational Development in the City of Fehring/Styria</i>	63
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Austria: An Introduction	67
5.2. <i>Management by Objectives in the Field of Compulsory Schooling</i>	70
5.3. <i>INKOBA: Inter-Communal Settlement Projects and Business Parks in Upper Austria</i>	75
5.4. <i>Austrian Conference of Spatial Planning: ÖROK</i>	80
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Austria: An Introduction	86
6.2. <i>Open Government Initiative Vienna</i>	89
6.3. <i>People’s Participation in Vorarlberg: Bürgerräte and Gemeindeentwicklungsprojekte Götzis/Langenegg</i>	93
6.4. <i>Participatory Budget in the Vienna District of Margareten</i>	100

Structure of Local Government

4.2. Inter-Municipal Development Process ‘Lienzer Talboden’ Future Space

Oskar Januschke and Jasmina Steiner, *City of Lienz*

Alexandra Schantl, *KDZ Centre for Public Administration Research Austria*

Relevance of the Practice

The ‘Lienzer Talboden future space’⁸⁸ is a good example for urban-rural cooperation between 15 communities in a challenging geographical and topographical area situated in the Austrian alpine space on the border to Italy. It is aimed at working together to shape the future development and positioning of this area, as a competitive business and residential location in Tyrol. The ‘Lienzer Talboden future space’ includes one urban local government (ULG) and 14 rural local governments (RLGs).

Description of the Practice

Competitive Business and Residential Location in Tyrol as an Impetus for Development across the Region

In 2013, the 15 communities of Ainet, Amlach, Assling, Dölsach, Gaimberg, Iselsberg-Stronach, Lavant, Leisach, Lienz, Nikolsdorf, Nußdorf-Debant, Oberlienz, Schlaiten, Thurn and Tristach devised a joint strategic development process with the aim of achieving close urban-rural collaboration on infrastructure issues, settlement policy, business development and administrative cooperation. The external approach is focused on the area’s positioning as a focal point and trigger in the functional interconnected region including Upper Carinthia and the Pustertal valley in South Tyrol. The advantages and benefits of this strategic urban-rural design bring an increase in efficiency, effectiveness and agglomeration effects. The 15 communities in the ‘Lienzer Talboden’ encompass an area of 471 km², 28,000 inhabitants, a working population of around 18,000 and a high concentration of infrastructure, leisure and educational facilities, forming a social and commercial center in this inter-regional, inter-connected area. Its proximity to the border of South Tyrol/Italy highlight the special significance and responsibility of the ‘Lienzer Talboden future space’ as a focal point of infrastructure, momentum and innovation for the development of the surrounding region.

⁸⁸ See KDZ, ‘Zukunftsraum Lienzer Talboden’ (*stadtregionen.at*, 2019) <<https://www.stadtregionen.at/lienz>> accessed 7 November 2019.

Process – A spatial and thematically integrated approach to the development of 15 communities

Following the launch event in 2013, a comprehensive review of the strengths and development potential at an intra-regional level was carried out as part of a multi-stage development process, moderated and supervised by the Institute for Location, Regional and Municipal Development (ISK). Another step raised the question of ‘where do we want to and how can we collaborate closely in the future as the ‘Lienzer Talboden future space’, establishing and adapting the fields of activity for future collaboration between the 15 communities based on this and defining concrete measures.

Since May 2015, the result of this has been a proposal from the committees of the ‘Planungsverband 36’ planning association for an ‘integrated location and business development concept’ for the ‘Lienzer Talboden future space’ which represents a conceptual basis for implementing measures during the ongoing LEADER period. The mayors of the ‘Planungsverband 36’ association are working together on nine fields of activity – business development and area management, tourist destination and infrastructure development, collective transport policy, specialization in the education sector, administrative cooperation, joint management of sport and leisure facilities and coordinated cross-community energy policy measures - with each accomplishment reinforcing the inter-municipal cooperation between the 15 communities.

The spatially integrated approach for the ‘Lienzer Talboden future space’ will be defined in relation to neighboring regions as open and not territorially restricted. There is the potential to implement another step towards spatial cooperation in the spirit of the European Grouping of Territorial Cooperation (EGTC)⁸⁹ through the urban-rural cooperation with Spittal an der Drau, Hermagor (Upper Carinthia) and Bruneck (South Tyrol/Italy) and to develop a strategic network for cross-border collaboration.

Regional Governance, Independent Development – From Conventional Management to Regional Conferences

Based on the experiences of the mayors and administrative bodies that political-administrative management, trust and understanding and transparency and tolerance represent key success factors in inter-municipal collaboration which extend beyond territorial community borders, the heads of the planning association for the development of the urban-rural collaboration as elected body devised and successfully applied a multi-stage regional governance approach with closed-session meetings, workshops, educational excursions, formal association meetings, organizational consultations and decisions by the relevant communities (executive board and municipal council) through new information tools such as the ‘regional conferences’ as a discussion and consultation forum for the representatives of the 15 member communities. The development process will be formally supported by the

⁸⁹ European Grouping of Territorial Cooperation (EGTC), tool for cross-border cooperation and collaboration.

'Planungsverband 36, Lienz und Umgebung' association – a municipal association established in accordance with the Tyrolean Spatial Planning Law. The whole process is financed by the 'Planungsverband 36' and the 'Lienz und Umgebung' association through membership fees of the municipalities, with EU funding through Interreg and LEADER and with financial support of the Land Tyrol. Furthermore, the City of Lienz is providing human resources (personnel) to managing the process.

According to the European Union definition, the term 'governance' can be understood as follows: '(...) rules, processes and behavior that affect the way in which powers are exercised at European level, particularly as regards openness, participation, accountability and coherence (...)'.⁹⁰ At the level of the planning association, this means in particular that regional experiences and conditions must be taken into account in the development of political suggestions. In order to apply this approach to the 'Planungsverband 36, Lienz und Umgebung', a regional governance structure was developed for the 'Lienzer Talboden future space' as part of the inter-municipal development process, focusing both on a bottom-up and top-down principle and which can subsequently be expanded to a multi-level governance system, enabling the 'Planungsverband 36, Lienz und Umgebung' association to position itself in strategic and organizational terms as a transnational organizational unit and therefore making the location of these 15 communities more attractive and competitive. The following overview presents the regional governance approach of the 'Lienzer Talboden future space'.

The regional governance approach of the 'Lienzer Talboden future space' involves a regional conference at the top-down principle level to which all local councilors will be invited to find out more about the project and regional developments, so that they can then reach unanimous decisions in the respective council meetings, wherever possible. The mayor conference level includes both association committee and association meetings. During these meetings, recommendations from the working groups will be discussed in regards to the following courses of action in the projects which were collectively devised during the initial phase of the inter-municipal development process and decided upon by the 'Planungsverband 36, Lienz und Umgebung'. To conclude, the development process combines and applies formal (*Gemeindeverband*) and informal (round tables, conferences etc.) cooperation forms and tools. However, it has been for the first time that an inter-municipal cooperation has become a registered trademark ('Zukunftsraum Lienzer Talboden') which facilitates both marketing and communication.

⁹⁰ Commission of the European Communities, 'European Governance A White Paper' COM(2001) 428, 1.

Figure 8: Regional Governance ‘Lienzer Talboden future space’⁹¹

Assessment of the Practice

In the tradition of inter-municipal cooperation in Austria the example of ‘Lienzer Talboden future space’ on the one hand contributes to reinforcing the inter-municipal cooperation between 15 municipalities in a challenging topographical Austrian area. On the other hand, it meets the relatively new approach in Austria to further developing and strengthening functional areas⁹². This is also in line with the increasing importance of functional areas and Macro regions (e.g. Alpine Space) in the EU-context. With its governance approach and the wide range of cooperation fields this example furthermore relates to all other report sections of the Austrian Country Report.

⁹¹ Planungsverband 36, ‘Lienz und Umgebung’ (2018).

⁹² See Österreichische Raumordnungskonferenz ÖROK, ‘Kooperationsplattform Stadtregionen’ (ÖROK, 2020) <<https://www.oerok.gv.at/raum/themen/stadtregionen>>; — ‘Regionale Handlungsebene stärken’ (ÖROK, 2020) <<https://www.oerok.gv.at/raum/themen/weitere-themen/regionale-handlungsebene>> accessed 20 November 2019.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Schantl A, Hochholdinger N and Rücker L, 'Stadtregionen in Österreich. Regionale Solidarität als Voraussetzung' (2019) 2 Forum Public Management 18

<<https://www.kdz.eu/de/content/stadtregionen-%C3%B6sterreich-regionale-solidarit%C3%A4t-als-voraussetzung>>

— 'Stadtregionen anerkennen' (2018) 3 Forum Public Management 10

<<https://www.kdz.eu/de/content/stadtregionen-ankennen>>

Website of the 'Zukunftsraum Lienzer Talboden'

<<http://www.zukunftsraumlienzertalboden.at/zukunftsraum/vision/>>

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

